

Multi-Strategy Optimization Approach for Location Privacy and Latency Trade-Offs in 6G Networks

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Abstract—Location-based services (LBS) are expected to play a foundational role in future 6G networks. However, they inherently raise privacy concerns due to the exposure of users' location data. To investigate the tradeoff between privacy and the QoS performance of LBS, we model the joint allocation of radio, processing, link, and routing resources under both privacy and latency constraints as a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) problem. We propose a privacy-preserving scheme that perturbs user locations using Laplace noise and leverages system resources to enhance privacy, albeit at the cost of some quality of service (QoS). By evaluating multiple optimization strategy variants, we quantify the privacy-latency tradeoff. In the considered scenario under low system load, the variant satisfying both privacy and latency constraints (PS-SL) strictly guarantees users' privacy while having only a 3% drop in the served users metric compared to privacy-cancellation baselines. Under high system load, PS-SL performance drops by not more than 17.3%, while achieving the least execution time among all strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

As mobile networks continue to evolve, the demand for higher data rates, lower latency, and increased reliability becomes increasingly critical. Emerging applications such as extended reality (XR), autonomous systems, and smart industries are pushing the limits of existing systems. Future 6G networks are being designed to offer unprecedented performance levels, enabling seamless connectivity, real-time responsiveness, massive data rates, very low latency, etc. [1].

Among the present trends, location-based services continue to draw focus and are anticipated to play a more prominent role in 6G networks. These include applications such as navigation, ride sharing, fitness apps, XR, among others [2]. Other applications could benefit from being location-aware to optimize their performance and the quality of service (QoS) for users. These include applications that optimize resource reservation for edge computing, distributed or federated learning, and more. Being location-aware would allow these applications to reserve resources efficiently, ensuring they meet the QoS requirements of users or clients.

On the other hand, exposing exact locations puts users at risk of privacy violations. Malicious actors, including malicious insiders within the application or external attackers exploiting system vulnerabilities, could exploit such exposure to track, monitor, or harm users. This has driven researchers to develop privacy-preserving schemes aimed at mitigating the risks associated with sharing such sensitive information. A commonly known privacy-preserving mechanism is Differential Privacy (DP). Epsilon-DP (ϵ -DP) is a mechanism designed to satisfy users' privacy requirements by injecting noise into the data. The noise follows a Laplace distribution, such that the lower the value of ϵ , the higher the noise, and thus, the stronger the privacy guarantees. In the context of location privacy, ϵ -DP would inject noise into the coordinates of the location, making the location perceived by the application different from the exact location [3].

While perturbing location data can help reduce the exposure of sensitive information, it comes at a cost. Many decisions rely on the assumption that location data is accurate. For instance, a machine learning (ML) application utilizing edge servers for training or inference may reserve resources on specific servers, expecting to meet the required QoS targets. However, if the location data is inaccurate, the resulting reservations may lead to discrepancies between the expected and actual latency and reliability.

In this work, we address the problem of radio, link, and processing resource allocation under joint privacy and QoS constraints. The key idea is that we aim to provide the location-based application with users' fake locations and users' fake associations with access points instead of sharing actual information. In fact, the LBS, the servers, the links, etc, could be owned by different vendors. So it remains important to avoid sharing the exact location information, in case a party in the network gets compromised. Hence, users' data are forwarded from the actual access points to the perceived ones before being delivered to the assigned processing servers. The goal is to exploit the system resources to tolerate small increases in delay, within QoS limits, in exchange for satisfying privacy or even providing additional privacy guarantees. This additional routing overhead complicates the ability of processing edge servers to figure out the exact location of users, providing a layer of privacy to users.

The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- We model the joint radio, link, routing, and processing resource allocation problem under privacy and latency constraints using a two-phase mixed integer linear programming (MILP) framework. The first phase aims to enhance the privacy guarantees of users by exploiting the system resources, while the second allocates the resources after perturbing the location in accordance with the assigned privacy guarantees.
- To investigate the privacy-latency tradeoff, we evaluate multiple MILP variants that reflect different strategies, including strict enforcement of both privacy and latency requirements, best-effort latency under privacy constraints, and cases where privacy is canceled.
- Finally, the implemented variants provide insights into the privacy-latency tradeoffs, highlighting the privacy gains of the proposed model over privacy-cancellation baselines.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The related work in the area of privacy and QoS-constrained resource allocation is reviewed in section II. Section III formulates the problem and introduces the MILP approach. Section IV describes the simulation setup and presents the results and discussion. Finally, Section V concludes the paper, presenting the future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Radio and computing resource allocation have been widely studied in the literature. In [4], a MILP-based radio allocation model is proposed, allocating resource blocks (RBs), modulation and coding schemes (MCS), and power assignment.

Still, it is limited to a single base station. [5] jointly allocates RBs, fronthaul, and processing capacity via an integer linear programming (ILP) formulation. [6] considers service-aware allocation under delay and fronthaul constraints, while [7] and [8] focus on latency minimization through joint radio-compute allocation. Unlike these, [9] proposes an MILP that minimizes energy consumption across radio and computing allocation, and [10] introduces a low-complexity matching-based alternative. All these works tackle the resource allocation problem without considering the privacy aspect.

On the other hand, some works have considered the privacy aspect. [11] addresses the challenge of maintaining user privacy in vehicular networks while ensuring efficient data transmission. It analyzes the tradeoff between data throughput and location privacy in vehicle-to-infrastructure communication. Authors use reinforcement learning (RL) to determine the noise added to obfuscate the location. However, they do not tackle the issue of dynamic reinforced privacy guarantees nor do they allocate multiple resources such as link or processing resources. In [12], the authors propose a reinforcement learning-based task offloading strategy that integrates differential privacy by perturbing users' locations. Unlike our work, it does not explicitly model or jointly optimize radio, routing, and computing resources under QoS constraints, nor does it tune the privacy parameter. The paper [13] presents a deep reinforcement learning-based approach to optimize task offloading considering both delay and privacy in multi-user multi-access edge computing (MEC) systems. It protects privacy in location and usage patterns by disguising offloading decisions and sending redundant tasks. In [14], the authors introduce a power allocation strategy for wireless localization to guarantee a minimum location secrecy metric (LSM). The goal is to optimize transmit power to ensure the eavesdropper's ability to infer location remains below a threshold.

In this paper, we jointly model and optimize radio, routing, and computing resources while integrating tunable differential privacy parameters for location-based services. Our approach studies the tradeoff between privacy and latency. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first MILP-based formulation that integrates multi-resource allocation with QoS constraints and tunable differential privacy guarantees.

III. THE MILP MODEL

In this section, we present the system model then we formulate the problem using MILP.

A. System model

We consider a location-based application that leverages edge servers to process users' data while meeting QoS requirements, such as minimum average throughput and maximum latency. This application can be any service that benefits from users' location information to reserve radio, link, and processing resources accordingly.

Consider a set of users \mathcal{U} and a set of nodes \mathcal{N} . The nodes consist of aerial and ground base stations, but only ground stations are equipped with edge servers. A user should be associated with a node that acts as an access point, and the user must also be associated with a node that has an edge server to process their data. This node may not necessarily be the same as the access point. Hence, a user's data can pass through several relay nodes before arriving at the assigned server. While users access these nodes through wireless communication, ground nodes are connected by high-speed ground links, whereas aerial base stations are connected to each other and to ground stations via sufficiently high-speed aerial links (i.e., using mmWave).

Our model assumes that users do not share their actual locations with the location-based service (LBS). Instead, they report perturbed (fake) locations generated using differential privacy, which adds controlled noise to obscure their real positions. Based on the reported location, each user is perceived to be associated, at the radio level, with the access point (AP) closest to the fake location, referred to as the perceived AP.

To preserve privacy, the actual data path is hidden from the LBS. Users connect to their true APs, but their data is rerouted to the perceived AP before continuing toward the processing servers. This additional routing overhead, handled by either the LBS itself or by a trusted third party, introduces additional latency but substantially complicates the LBS's ability to infer users' true locations. The third party is responsible for managing radio resource allocation, traffic routing, and assigning edge processing servers, acting as an intermediary that shields sensitive information.

From the LBS's perspective, only the perturbed locations are visible. It assumes that users are connected to the perceived APs and thus bases its processing resource reservations at the edge servers on these perceived associations. As a consequence of the proposed privacy mechanism, users may not be served by the edge servers closest to their real location, potentially affecting QoS. To limit the LBS's ability to compromise users' location privacy, the LBS cannot optimize its processing resource reservations based on true user positions; it must adapt these reservations by monitoring observable QoS outcomes (e.g., achieved latency, percentage of served users, etc.) and dynamically adjusting reservations accordingly. As an example, a machine learning (ML) inference task would ideally run on the edge server closest to the user for minimal delay. However, doing so could compromise location privacy. This introduces a privacy-performance tradeoff, where user data may travel longer paths or be processed at less optimal servers to obscure real locations.

B. Problem formulation

In this part, we model our problem as a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) problem, which is to be solved by the LBS or by a trusted third party. Denote by $d_{u,i}^2$ the squared distance between the fake position of user u and node i . Let α_i^u be a binary variable indicating whether a user u is associated (i.e., perceived association) with node i as a perceived access point, and \min_u be an auxiliary variable used to capture the node that is closest to the user. The following constraints together assign a unique perceived (fake) access point to each user based on their perturbed locations.

$$\min_u \leq d_{u,i}^2, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_i^u \cdot d_{u,i}^2 = \min_u, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_i^u = 1, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}. \quad (3)$$

If the values of $d_{u,i}^2$ are known in advance, α_i^u can be recomputed by assigning each user u to the closest node i based on $d_{u,i}^2$, to reduce the burden on the solver. Let β_i^u be a binary variable used to indicate if the data of user u is forwarded to the perceived access point i . Let y_j^u be a binary variable indicating whether the server at node j processes the data of user u . Additionally, let $x_{i,j}^u$ be a binary variable that determines whether the data of user u is forwarded from node i to node j .

$$\beta_i^u \leq \alpha_i^u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_j^u \leq 1, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \beta_i^u = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_j^u, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (6)$$

$$y_j^u + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} x_{j,k}^u \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_j^u + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} x_{i,j}^u = y_j^u + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} x_{j,k}^u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, j \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (8)$$

Constraints (4) ensure that β_i^u is only activated at the assigned perceived node (i.e., access point). In addition, (5) guarantee that no more than one server can process a user's data, and (6) ensure that if $\beta_i^u = 1$, then there exists a unique server that processes the user's data. Constraints (7) ensure that, in case a node j is used by u , this node either processes the data of u at the corresponding edge server, or forwards it to another node, but not both. In such a case (8), aided by (7), ensure such a node is either a perceived fake access point node or a receiving node, but not both.

In the following, (9) ensure that, for the delivery of a user's data between the fake perceived access point and the server, a link is used in only one direction, and (10) ensure that there is no link between a node and itself (i.e., illogical). (11) and (12) respectively enforce that at a specific node, no more than one link can carry incoming data for this user, and no more than one link can forward this user's data away from this node.

$$x_{i,j}^u + x_{j,i}^u \leq 1, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (9)$$

$$x_{i,i}^u = 0, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} x_{i,j}^u \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} x_{i,j}^u \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (12)$$

Recalling that α_i^u designates the fake user association with an access point, data must be delivered from the real access point to this perceived one. Let λ_i^u be a binary variable indicating if user u uses node i as the real access point, while $z_{i,j}^u$ is defined similarly to $x_{i,j}^u$, but $z_{i,j}^u$ is responsible for routing data from the real to the perceived access point.

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \lambda_i^u = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} \beta_j^u, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (13)$$

$$\beta_j^u + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} z_{j,k}^u \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (14)$$

$$\lambda_j^u + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} z_{i,j}^u = \beta_j^u + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}} z_{j,k}^u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, j \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (15)$$

In the equations above, (13) ensure that if $\beta_i^u = 1$ for the user, then a real access point association must exist for the user. The constraints (14) ensure that a node cannot be the perceived fake access point and simultaneously have an outgoing link via $z_{i,j}^u$, since the latter's role is to deliver data from the real to the perceived access point. Moreover, (15) guarantee that if node j is the real association for user u , then it is either also the declared perceived access point, or it has an outgoing link to another intermediate node or the destination. Furthermore, it guarantees that if the node is the reported fake access point but it is not the real access point, then it must have an incoming link that carries the data of u . Otherwise, if it is only an intermediate node, it must have one incoming and one outgoing link.

The following constraints apply the same principle as (9), (10), (11), (12), but for the routing from the real access point to the perceived one.

$$z_{i,j}^u + z_{j,i}^u \leq 1, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (16)$$

$$z_{i,i}^u = 0, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} z_{i,j}^u \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} z_{i,j}^u \leq 1, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (19)$$

We note that a link can be used twice: once in the delivery from the real access point to the perceived one, and again in the delivery from the latter to the server. This increases the delay, but it is the price we are willing to pay to improve privacy. Denote by $C_{i,j}$ the capacity of the link connecting nodes i and j , by $data^u$ the amount of data to be sent by user u each second, and by e_j the processing capabilities of server j measured in bits per second. The transmission time for user u in the links and the processing time, respectively, are:

$$T_{trans}^u = \sum_{i,j \in \mathcal{N}} (x_{i,j}^u + z_{i,j}^u) \cdot \frac{data^u}{C_{i,j}}, \quad T_{proc}^u = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_j^u \cdot \frac{data^u}{e_j}.$$

Each user has a specific time requirement to be respected, denoted as T_{req}^u . The time requirement is the maximum delay for the chunk of data sent every second. The constraints (20) ensure that a user's delay requirement is respected, (21) ensure that a server processes no more than its capabilities, and (22) ensure a link cannot carry more than its capacity.

$$T_{proc}^u + T_{trans}^u \leq T_{req}^u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} y_j^u \cdot data^u \leq e_j, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} (x_{i,j}^u + x_{j,i}^u + z_{i,j}^u + z_{j,i}^u) \cdot data^u \leq C_{i,j}, \quad \forall i, j \in \mathcal{N} \quad (22)$$

Next, we consider the radio allocation constraints. To assign users to base stations and allocate resource blocks (RBs) and modulation and coding schemes (MCS), we introduce the binary variable $\chi_{r,m}^{i,u}$, which indicates whether user u is using resource block r of base station (node) i with MCS m . The binary variable $\zeta_{s,m}^u$ is used to track the total number of resource blocks along the MCS index used by user u . The binary variable $\kappa_m^{i,u}$ tracks the MCS index used by a user, ensuring that the index is unique across all its resource blocks. The transmission power of user u over resource block r of node i is represented by $p_r^{i,u}$, and P_{Tx}^{\max} is the maximum total transmission power per user. The channel gain between user u and node i over resource block r is denoted by $g_r^{i,u}$. The SNR threshold required for using MCS m is γ_m^{th} , and σ^u represents the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). The throughput achieved when using a total of s RBs and MCS index m is captured by $R_{s,m}$, while R_{min}^u denotes the minimum throughput required by user u per millisecond. The following constraints manage the radio allocation:

$$\sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \chi_{r,m}^{i,u} \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, r \in \mathcal{R}, \quad (23)$$

$$\sum_{s \in \mathbb{N} \cap [1, |\mathcal{R}|]} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \zeta_{s,m}^u (R_{s,m} - R_{min}^u) \geq 0, \quad u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (24)$$

$$\sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} p_r^{i,u} \leq P_{Tx}^{\max}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (25)$$

$$p_r^{i,u} \leq M \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \chi_{r,m}^{i,u}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, r \in \mathcal{R}, \quad (26)$$

$$\chi_{r,m}^{i,u} \leq \kappa_m^{i,u}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, r \in \mathcal{R}, m \in \mathcal{M}, \quad (27)$$

$$\sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \kappa_m^{i,u} \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, \quad (28)$$

$$\kappa_m^{i,u} \leq \lambda_i^u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, i \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M}, \quad (29)$$

$$g_r^{i,u} p_r^{i,u} \geq \gamma_m^{th} \sigma^u \chi_{r,m}^{i,u}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, u \in \mathcal{U}, r \in \mathcal{R}, m \in \mathcal{M}, \quad (30)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} \chi_{r,m}^{i,u} = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{N} \cap [1, |\mathcal{R}|]} s \times \zeta_{s,m}^u, \quad u \in \mathcal{U}, m \in \mathcal{M}, \quad (31)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} y_i^u = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{N} \cap [1, |\mathcal{R}|]} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \zeta_{s,m}^u, \quad u \in \mathcal{U}. \quad (32)$$

The constraints defined by (23) ensure that a resource block from node i can be used by at most one user with a unique MCS. In addition, (24) guarantee that each user is assigned enough RBs and an appropriate MCS index to meet their minimum throughput requirement. Constraints (25) limit the total transmission power used by a user across all their RBs to the maximum power budget, while (26) ensure the transmission power is zero if the user does not use the RB. Here, M is the Big-M notation, a sufficiently large value. While constraints (27) track the MCS index used by the user, ensuring that the index is unique across the user's RBs, as stipulated by (28). Furthermore, (29) ensure that only $\kappa_m^{i,u}$, corresponding to the real association of user u tracked by λ_i^u , is activated. While we could have omitted λ_i^u and used $\kappa_m^{i,u}$ directly, we chose to separate the radio allocation formulation from earlier parts. Modern MILP solvers can handle such redundancies efficiently without affecting performance. Constraints (30) ensure that the MCS index can only be used if the SINR constraint is satisfied; and (31) are used to count the total number of RBs used by each user. Note that we ignore potential interference for this analysis, focusing on the tradeoff between privacy and latency, rather than interference management. Finally, (32) links the radio allocation to the processing server allocation, ensuring that both (i.e., one server and one (MCS, RB) pair) are assigned for a user or neither is activated.

Denote by d_x^u and d_y^u the x and y coordinates of the user, and d_x^i and d_y^i those of the node. The perturbations μ_{x,ϵ_u}^u and μ_{y,ϵ_u}^u follow a Laplace distribution with mean zero and scale parameter $\frac{\Delta F}{\epsilon_u}$. ΔF is the maximum variation in the location (i.e., if a coordinate varies between -2 and 2 , the maximum variation is 4), while ϵ_u is the privacy guarantee. The formula of the squared perturbed distance between user u and node i , considering the noise perturbation, is expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{u,i}^2 &= ((d_x^u + \mu_{x,\epsilon_u}^u) - d_x^i)^2 + ((d_y^u + \mu_{y,\epsilon_u}^u) - d_y^i)^2 \\ &= (d_x^u - d_x^i)^2 + 2(d_x^u - d_x^i)\mu_{x,\epsilon_u}^u + \mu_{x,\epsilon_u}^u{}^2 \\ &\quad + (d_y^u - d_y^i)^2 + 2(d_y^u - d_y^i)\mu_{y,\epsilon_u}^u + \mu_{y,\epsilon_u}^u{}^2. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the expectation of the perturbation and the squared perturbation is:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mu_{x,\epsilon_u}^u] = \mathbb{E}[\mu_{y,\epsilon_u}^u] = 0, \quad \mathbb{E}[\mu_{x,\epsilon_u}^u{}^2] = \mathbb{E}[\mu_{y,\epsilon_u}^u{}^2] = \frac{2(\Delta F)^2}{\epsilon_u^2}$$

Denoting by $(d_{u,i}^{real})^2$ the true squared distance between a user and a node when the noise is zero, the expected squared distance becomes:

$$\mathbb{E}[d_{u,i}^2] = (d_x^u - d_x^i)^2 + (d_y^u - d_y^i)^2 + \frac{4(\Delta F)^2}{\epsilon_u^2} = (d_{u,i}^{real})^2 + \frac{4(\Delta F)^2}{\epsilon_u^2}.$$

We assume each user has a privacy guarantee requirement. Smaller ϵ_u leads to higher noise, which indicates higher privacy. We define an auxiliary variable $\tau_u = \frac{1}{\epsilon_u^2}$, and use $\tau_u^{req} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_{u,req}^2}$ to capture the privacy requirement.

Solving for the expectation, constraints (1), (2) become:

$$\min_u \leq (d_{u,i}^{real})^2 + 4\tau_u(\Delta F)^2, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall i \in \mathcal{N}, \quad (33)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} \alpha_i^u \cdot ((d_{u,i}^{real})^2 + 4\tau_u(\Delta F)^2) = \min_u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}. \quad (34)$$

We also add (35) to ensure the model does not modify the privacy parameter for users it fails to admit.

$$\tau_u \leq M \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}} y_i^u, \quad \forall u \in \mathcal{U}. \quad (35)$$

The problem is solved in two phases. The first solves the expectation to guarantee the privacy:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & w_1 \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_j^u + w_2 \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \tau_u \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (3) \dots (35) \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

where w_1 and w_2 are weights used to control the balance between reinforcing privacy and maximizing the number of users served. The goal is to prioritize serving users while respecting their privacy requirements, and, on top of that, the model can further enhance privacy.

After solving the problem, we obtain τ_u , then $\epsilon_u = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tau_u}}$. From there, the perturbation is sampled using Laplace distribution, and the following problem will be solved:

$$\begin{aligned} \max \quad & \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_j^u \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & (1) \dots (32) \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

In addition, it is possible to modify the optimization problem to include the total latency as a penalty. This would push the model to reduce the total latency and could be paired with relaxing the latency requirements by removing the corresponding constraints. The objective becomes:

$$\max \quad w_1 \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} y_j^u + w_2 \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} (T_{proc}^u + T_{trans}^u). \quad (38)$$

The goal would be to ensure that a user is served, then the latency would be optimized.

Next, we describe the variants of the MILP model, followed by the simulation results.

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

We analyze the performance of the joint privacy and QoS model considering multiple variants of the MILP problem.

A. MILP Strategies

In this work, we design and evaluate five MILP-based strategies for privacy-aware resource allocation. The first strategy is the one introduced in the paper, while the remaining strategies are variations derived from it. The strategies are:

- **Privacy Maximization - Satisfied Latency (PM-SL)**: it consists of two phases, where the first phase satisfies and maximizes users' privacy, while the second maximizes the total number of served users.
- **Privacy Satisfaction - Satisfied Latency (PS-SL)**: in this variant the privacy is set to the requirement. Compared to the one above, the first phase is removed and only the second phase is considered.
- **Privacy Satisfaction - Best Effort Latency (PS-BEL)**: similar to PS-SL, but the latency constraints are relaxed, and the

(a) Served Users (Normal Load).

(b) Served Users (Low Load).

Fig. 1: Served Users under different system loads.

model aims to maximize the number of served users while it minimizes the total latency among served users.

- *Privacy Cancellation - Satisfied Latency (PC-SL)*: a variant where privacy constraints are canceled, focusing solely on satisfying latency requirements.
- *Privacy Cancellation - Best Effort Latency (PC-BEL)*: a version where privacy constraints are canceled and latency is handled on a best-effort basis in the objective function.

Both privacy cancellation schemes are used as baselines, given that they mimic the available algorithms in the literature without implementing privacy. We had to adapt the model from [10], so that it includes routing and link resources. This allows us to make a comparison of this work with it.

B. Simulation Settings

We consider the following simulation parameters. We consider 15 nodes such as 5 are ground base stations that are connected to processing servers, while 10 are aerial base stations with no servers, acting as access points only. Each has 20 resource blocks (RBs) for transmission. Additionally, the number of users varies from 5 to 25. To select users' location, the x and y coordinates follow a uniform distribution within the -2 to $+2$ km range. For nodes that are either ground or aerial base stations, we also include the z-coordinate chosen within the range of 0 to 20 meters. In contrast, that of users is assumed to be 0 for simplicity. The sensitivity parameter for sampling the noise following the Laplace distribution, ΔF , is set to 4000 meters. The processing capacity of network nodes is randomly chosen within the range of 20 to 30 Mbps. Each node has two links (i.e., wireless or ground cables) such that the link capacity varies between 20 and 40 Mbps. The privacy requirement parameter for each user is represented by epsilon (ϵ) and is randomly assigned within the range of 0.01 to 10. The delay requirement is defined as the delay for each 1 Mb of data and is set between 0.5 and 2 seconds per Mb, while the rate requirement ranges from 5 to 10 Mbps for each user. The system supports 14 different modulation and coding schemes (MCS) with a noise spectral density of -174 dBm/Hz. We set the maximum transmit power P_{\max}^{Tx} to 23 dBm, and the bandwidth per resource block is set to 180kHz. Additionally, we use the transport block size (TBS) from 3GPP standard to measure the throughput as a function of the MCS and the number of RBs.

From [10], we use the set of SINR thresholds (γ_{th}), which ranges from -6.658 to 19.809 dB, and we use the ABG model in [15] to determine the channel gains.

Regarding the objective function, we set $w_1 = 1$ and $w_2 = 10^{-6}$ for privacy maximization. This ensures that maximizing users' privacy never outweighs serving additional users, noting the limited number of users and the ceiling of $\tau_u \leq 10^4$. When including the sum of latency of all users in the objective, we use $w_2 = -10^{-4}$ to avoid scenarios where minimizing latency could lead the model to reject users.

C. Numerical results analysis

To analyze the results, we repeat the simulation 100 times and average the results. We plot the curves considering multiple metrics, showing the 95% confidence intervals.

In Fig. 1a, we plot the number of served users as a function of the total number of users in the system. We compare this to a low-load scenario in Fig. 1b. In the latter, we relaxed the system load by setting the link and processing capacities to range between 20 and 100 Mbps, and relaxing user delay requirements to span between 1s and 4s. This results in greater transmission and processing resources, and more tolerant delay constraints. As seen in the figures, all models serve more users under low load, as expected when resources are abundant.

PM-SL aims to exploit the system's resources to maximize privacy. Since privacy is maximized based on the expected perceived distance after applying Laplace noise, the second phase of decision-making must address cases where the sampled noise results in a higher-than-expected perceived distance. In such cases, users may fail to meet their latency requirements. Because most resources may have been exhausted to maximize privacy, any unexpected increase in distance can prevent satisfying QoS constraints. This explains why maximizing privacy can degrade QoS, making **PM-SL** the worst performer in terms of served users. Under low load, **PC-SL** and **PS-BEL** perform similarly, since latency is not a major constraint when resources are ample. However, under high load, **PS-BEL** benefits from its flexibility; it is allowed to relax the latency constraint to serve more users. As for privacy-cancellation schemes (**PC-SL** and **PC-BEL**), they are expected to serve more users as they do not dedicate resources to meet the privacy needs. Under low load, they perform similarly due to non-restrictive latency constraints. At high load, variants employing Best-Effort-Latency benefit from latency relaxation, enabling higher admission. At high number of users counts, we set a 600-second time limit for the solver. Due to **PC-BEL**'s expanded search space (as a result of relaxing latency constraints), it often hits the time limit before reaching optimality. This explains the observed performance drop of **PC-BEL** relative to its **PC-SL** counterpart. Furthermore, **PS-SL** experiences up to 17% performance drop compared to **PC-SL** at high load. However, the drop is limited to 3% at low-load in exchange for strictly satisfying the privacy guarantees of users. This underscores the efficiency of **PS-SL** at guaranteeing both privacy and QoS in low-load scenarios.

Next, we plot the average variation in the privacy parameter ϵ across users in Fig. 2a. **PM-SL** is the only strategy that actively seeks to minimize ϵ values to enhance user privacy. When the number of users is low (i.e., low load), there is greater flexibility to reallocate resources toward privacy improvement. As the number of users increases, resource contention limits this flexibility, restricting the ability to improve privacy, leading to generally higher ϵ values. Fig. 2b illustrates the average delay violation for users admitted without satisfying their delay requirements. Here, violation is defined as the average amount by which users exceed their delay bounds. This explains

Fig. 2: Other Key Metrics.

what was discussed earlier regarding the SL vs BEL variants. **PC-BEL** benefits from its ability to tolerate such violations, enabling higher user admission than **PC-SL**, which strictly enforces delay requirements. Similarly, **PS-BEL** outperforms **PS-SL** by leveraging this flexibility.

Finally, Fig. 2c presents the total solver execution time versus the number of users. Simulations were conducted using Python 3.11.9 and Gurobi 12 on a computing cluster with Intel Xeon Gold 6230R CPUs (40 threads). The execution time includes Python overhead and Gurobi interface latency. **PS-SL** achieves the lowest execution time, ranging from a few seconds to approximately 23s on average when the number of users is 25. This suggests that MILP solvers may be feasible in non-real-time applications, such as distributed or federated learning, where delays in initialization are tolerable. Moreover, practical deployments could exploit hardware acceleration for faster computation. However, in highly dynamic environments requiring frequent reallocation, MILP-based approaches may be impractical. In such cases, lightweight heuristics or learning-based alternatives become necessary.

D. Key Takeaways

- **Uncontrolled privacy maximization harms QoS.** Increasing privacy at the cost of latency reduces user admission, necessitating a cap on additional privacy.
- **Latency relaxation can boost performance.** Relaxing delay constraints in high-load scenarios to serve more users.
- **Privacy enhancement is resource-sensitive.** As load increases, reducing ϵ becomes harder for **PM-SL**.
- **MILP suits static conditions.** It is usable when changes are infrequent; dynamic environments need heuristics or learning.
- **PS-LS offers the best tradeoff.** It meets privacy and latency requirements with the least execution time.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we studied the joint allocation of radio, link, routing, and processing resources for location-based services under privacy and latency constraints, aiming to study the latency-privacy tradeoff. We formulated the problem as a mixed integer linear program (MILP) and analyzed several variants that reflect this tradeoff. Our results show that the variant satisfying both latency and privacy constraints guarantees privacy and achieves high QoS at low load compared to privacy-cancellation baselines. At high system load, it incurs a limited performance degradation but achieves the least execution time. While MILP offers optimal solutions, its computational complexity makes it less suitable for dynamic or real-time environments. As a future direction, we aim to develop a learning-based solution to the MILP problem with faster execution time.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work is supported by the EC through the Horizon Europe/JU SNS project ROBUST-6G (Grant Agreement no. 101139068), the EU HORIZON MSCA-SE TRACE-V2X project (Grant No. 101131204) and the CY Initiative (grant "Investissements d'Avenir" ANR-16-IDEX-0008).

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